

1. Line diagram of a setup for measuring electroantennogram response of insects to volatile compounds.

in the antenna are amplified and displayed on the oscilloscope.

The response is usually a negative potential. Positive potentials may also be obtained, however, depending on the chemistry and biological activity of the compound involved (Fig. 2).

The amplitude of the response, which correlates with the frequency of generated nerve impulses, increases with

concentration of the chemical stimulus until a saturation level is reached.

Although it was thought that the electroantennogram technique did not permit conclusions about the behavioral significance of a compound (i.e., attractant or repellent), results from our laboratory and elsewhere suggest that compounds eliciting very high negative potential may be attractant at low con-

2. (a) A typical negative potential elicited in response to stimulation with 1-hexanol. (b) A positive potential elicited in response to thymol.

centrations while compounds eliciting positive potential may be repellents.

We have successfully used electroantennogram technique to study the role of volatiles in the resistance of rice plants to insects, identify rice plant volatiles that are biologically active, and identify pheromones of leafrollers and stem borers. ■

Density-dependent mortality of rice leafroller (LF) due to larval parasitization

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LF, a pyralid that feeds on rice leaves, is often attacked by parasitoids. More than 100 species from various regions have been recorded.

We studied the relationship between LF and its larval parasitoids in Victoria, Laguna, and Zaragosa, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, during 1989 wet season. Samples were taken at weekly (in Victoria) and biweekly (in Zaragosa) intervals from 2 wk after transplanting. A sample consisted of 20 hills from 1 m².

All LF larvae collected were placed individually in test tubes and brought to the laboratory for parasitoid emergence.

Mortality due to parasitization was expressed as *k*-value (a measure of killing power) by function, $k = \log(N/S)$, where *N* is total larvae collected and *S* the unparasitized larvae. Four density dependence models were fitted to the data using PROC NLIN available in SAS.

The models satisfactorily described the data, but the model according to Bellows (1981) provided the best fit. It has the basic form

$$k = aN^b$$

where *a* and *b* are constants. The parameter *b* determines density dependence.

Results showed that parasitization is directly density dependent. The mortality rate *k* changes in a negative acceleration as host density increases (Fig. 1).

We further plotted the *k* values against log host density in a time sequence (Fig. 2). It showed that density dependence was undercompensated because slope was $0 < b < 1$. Time lag was important and an anticlockwise spiral was apparent, indicating delayed density dependence.

Stability analysis showed that this relationship will inevitably result in dampening exponential growth of the LF population. Thus larval parasitoids play an extremely important role in checking LF abundance. ■

1. Plots of k -value against log density of LF larva in Victoria and Zaragosa, Philippines. The solid line is the best fit curve of Bellows' model: $k = aN^b$.

2. Density-dependent mortality (expressed as k -value) of LF due to larval parasitoids in relation to LF larva density. Data are serially linked to show the delayed density dependence.

Attractiveness of light color to selected predators of rice pests

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Light traps are commonly used to monitor insect pest populations in ricefields. We used different colors of light as attractants to rice insect pests in 1988 wet season in Calauan, Laguna, Philippines.

Several insect pests were most attracted to white and yellow lights. And light had the same attraction to various beneficial insects.

Four important predators of rice pests—*Microvelia* sp., *Cyrtorhinus* sp., *Opius* sp., and members of Formicidae family—were collected in significantly higher numbers from the white light trap compared to other light colors tested (see figure). Numbers from yellow, ultraviolet, and green light traps were moderate (see table). Even in traps with the least attractive colors of light (violet, blue, red, and orange), the four predator species were collected.

Spectrometric analysis of the light produced by the eight bulbs tested revealed that not one emitted the pure colors visible to the human eye (see table). Different color combinations, from violet to red, ranging from 4,000 to 7,300 Å, produce the eight colors distinct to human vision.

Among the eight colors of light tested the light emitted by the white bulb contained the most distinct color bands. These bands were contained in a range from 4,100 to 6,300 Å, which could be the most attractive color combination for the predator species observed in the light traps.

The attraction of the four predator species to white light, coupled with studies on actual predator population, natural mortality, and migratory habits could be used in a rice-pest predator monitoring system. ■

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.